

DETECTION ON CURING PROCESS OF LARGE THICKNESS COMPOSITE LAMINATE USING FIBER BRAGG GRATING

G. Zhang¹, L. Luo², T. Qiao³, B. Zhang⁴ and Y. Xu⁵

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, China, 2250898783@qq.com

² School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, China, 675491858@qq.com

³ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing, China, 18603278490@163.com

Keywords: Large thickness composite laminate; Fiber Bragg grating; Curing process; Monitoring

ABSTRACT

To investigate the temperature and strain history throughout the curing process of large thickness three-hundred-ply Kevlar/epoxy composite laminate which was 51 mm thick, the monitoring experiment was carried out. Specifically, fiber Bragg grating (FBG) temperature and strain sensors were adjacently embedded in the large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composite specimen to in situ monitor the temperature and strain evolution at 5 monitoring points along the thickness direction. The tested strain sensitivity constant (K_ϵ) and temperature sensitivity constant (K_T) of the FBGs were 1.263 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$ and 10.9 pm/ $^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Results show that the heat of the drastic exothermal reaction was the most significant factor affecting the temperature and strain of large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composites. The FBG temperature sensors used in Kevlar/epoxy composites will lead to great error if the temperature increases too fast. The peak temperature value on the outside of the Kevlar/epoxy composites is 134.18 $^\circ\text{C}$, while the peak temperature value on the inside of the specimen is 251.2 $^\circ\text{C}$, which has a 117 $^\circ\text{C}$ temperature difference between outer layer and inner layer. Curing residual strain on the outside of the Kevlar/epoxy composites is relatively smaller than that on the inner side of the specimen, and the two strain values are 537.66 $\mu\epsilon$ and 1180.63 $\mu\epsilon$. The maximum difference of residual strain between the outer and the internal layer is 642.97 $\mu\epsilon$. This paper will provide an approach for strain and temperature measurement of large thickness composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are widely used in numerous areas such as civil engineering, aerospace, automobile, ship and petroleum industries because of their virtue of light weight and high specific strength and stiffness compared with the traditional materials. Residual strain and stress can be induced during the manufacturing of FRP composites, which can reduce mechanical performance, dimensional stability and durability of composite structures, and both of them correlate closely with the process induced strain of prepreg [1-5]. Hence, it is essential to accurately monitor the evolution of strain during the curing process of FRP composites. By virtue of durable, reliable and small sensors which do not weaken the structure, the fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors are widely used in strain measurement [6-8]. In this work, FBG sensors were internally embedded into the 51 mm thick Kevlar/epoxy composite specimen and used to monitor strain and temperature in the curing process. A solution for strain and temperature measurement of large thickness composites will be presented in this paper.

2 THEORETICAL APPROACH

The sensing principle of FBG is based on a periodic perturbation of the refractive index along the fiber length. FBGs reflect light centered at a particular wavelength, termed as the Bragg wavelength. Fig. 1 shows the working principle of fiber Bragg grating.

Figure 1: Working principle of fiber Bragg grating.

The wavelength of the reflected light, λ_B , depends on the effective refractive index (n_{eff}) of the fiber core and the Bragg period (Λ) of the grating, according to the Bragg equation [9]:

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{\text{eff}} \Lambda \quad (1)$$

The sensor also exhibits a linear response to both strain and temperature, making it suitable for structure monitoring applications [10]. When strain ε in the sensor axial direction and temperature change ΔT are applied to the FBG, the spectrum centre wavelength λ_B shifts by:

$$\Delta\lambda_B = K_\varepsilon \varepsilon + K_T \Delta T \quad (2)$$

K_ε and K_T denote the strain and temperature sensitivity constants, respectively.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Calibration experiment of K_ε

The strain sensitivity constant was tested in the experiment. The FBG sensors were supplied by Yuguang Inc. with a diameter of 125 μm . One resistance strain gauge was welded on the centre of the tensile specimen along the tensile direction. Two FBG sensors were pasted on the specimen which were parallel to the strain gauge (shown in Fig. 2). The drawing speed of the tensile testing machine was 2 mm/min (shown in Fig. 3).

Figure 2: The resistance strain gauge and FBG sensors

Figure 3: The diagram of tensile testing

3.2 Monitoring experiment

The temperature sensitivity constant was tested in the experiment. The material considered here was Kevlar/epoxy fabric composite. The dimension of the three-hundred-ply woven Kevlar/epoxy fabrics used here were 175 mm×80 mm and about 51 mm thick. This research investigated the three-hundred-ply, hot-press processed woven laminates that are normally produced by the following method. The pressure was set at 6 bar before the temperature was increased at the rate of 0.5 °C/min from 25 °C up to 130 °C. Then, the temperature was held constantly for 120 minutes (temperature dwell). This was followed by a cooling phase down to the room temperature at the rate of 0.3 °C/min and a pressure relief. Five monitoring points (A, B, C, D and E) were chosen in the three-hundred-ply Kevlar/epoxy composite specimen along the thickness direction (shown in Fig. 4).

Figure 4: The diagram of Five monitoring points

Two types of FBGs were used in this work. The first FBGs (FBG-S) was subjected and sensitive to both strain and temperature, and the second FBGs (FBG-T) was inserted in a hermetic steel tube, enforced that the sensor is preserved from external mechanical strains and is only subjected to temperature. Fig. 5 shows the two types of FBGs. One FBG temperature sensor and two FBG strain sensors were assigned in every monitoring point. Due to the limitation of the outlet hole of the autoclave, only three thermocouples were used and embedded into the point A, C and E, respectively. Fig. 6 shows the distributions of sensors and thermocouple.

Figure 5: The two types of FBGs.

Figure 6: The distributions of FBGs and thermocouple

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 7, the scatter lines represent the actual wavelength collected from the FBG corresponding to the strain which is recorded from the strain gauge and the solid line is fitted by the value of the gradient of regression line. Figure 7 shows a very good linear relationship between wavelength collected from the FBG and strain of the strain gauge. The strain sensitivity constant (K_ϵ) of the FBGs was 1.263 pm/ $\mu\epsilon$.

Figure 7: The diagram of strain and wavelength

In Figure 8, the scatter lines represent the actual different wavelength collected from the FBG corresponding to the temperatures of thermocouple at point A, C and E respectively and the other three lines are fitted by the value of the gradient of regression line. The three temperature sensitivity constants were acquired and which were $K_{TA} = 10.9 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, $K_{TC} = 11.4 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ and $K_{TE} = 10.9 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Compared with the curves of the point A and E, the linearity of the curve from point C was poor especially between $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The main reason was that the drastic exothermal reaction causes the temperature to rise sharply (as can be seen from Fig. 9). The heating rate increases and the hysteresis of the FBG had a great influence on the curve linearity. Therefore, the temperature sensitivity constant is $K_T=10.9 \text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 8: The diagram of temperature and wavelength

The temperature history curves of the five monitoring points were shown in Fig. 9. During the heating process, the point A and E obviously heated up faster than the inner points. When it gets close to the curing temperature, the temperature at the point B, C, D, and E increased rapidly due to the severe curing reaction. The highest temperature of the point C increased up to $281.16 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Actually, the temperature measured by the thermocouple was $251.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The reason for the error was related to the sharp increasement in temperature. The maximum temperatures at the point B and D were $235.73 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $240.12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, which has shown little difference between them. The point A displayed the maximum temperature of $134.18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, only $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ higher than the curing temperature. The point E exhibited the maximum temperature of $161.35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature difference of $27 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was mainly due to the heat dissipation performance of the metal mold was much better than that of vacuum bag. The temperature gradient distribution was obvious in the curing process of large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composites. In addition, the maximum difference of temperature between the outer layer and the internal layer was $117 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 9: The temperature history curves

Fig.10 illustrates the strain curves of the five points throughout the curing process. This is a complex process, which involves the influence of temperature, curing shrinkage and mold interaction. Before the gelation of the resin, the strain changes caused by thermal deformation and resin flow of the prepreg were measured by FBG sensors. In the initial stage, the trend of strain at the point A was different from the strain at the other points, which was apparently affected by the thermal expansion of the mold. When the time reached around 200 minutes, the strain of the five points increased rapidly in a very short period of time. Before gelation of the resin, thermal expansion and solidification does not produce strains in theory. However, the strain curves increased mostly due to the excessively large thermal expansion from the heat of the drastic exothermal reaction and the frictional effect transferred to FBGs as the viscosity increased. In the thermal insulation platform stage, the resin reacted until it solidified completely. The curing shrinkage can be seen clearly only in the strain curve at the point E. Therefore, the heat of the drastic exothermal reaction was the most important factor affecting strain of large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composites. In the cooling stage, the strain curves fell down mainly due to the decreased temperature and the frictional effect transferred to FBGs. The minimum curing residual strain at the point A was $537.66 \mu\epsilon$, which was mainly affected by the mold. The residual strain at the point E was $669.10 \mu\epsilon$, which was mainly due to the direct effect of atmospheric pressure of 6 bar on the outer layer, which limits the strain development during the forming process. The residual strain values at the point B, C, and D were $1180.63 \mu\epsilon$, $925.66 \mu\epsilon$ and $1114.12 \mu\epsilon$ respectively. The strain gradient distribution was obvious in the curing process of large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composites. Additionally, the maximum difference of curing residual strain between the outer layer and the internal layer is $642.97 \mu\epsilon$.

Figure 10: The strain history curves

5 CONCLUSIONS

(1) It is feasible that FBG sensors can be used to monitor the temperature and strain produced in the curing process of large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composite laminate. When monitoring the temperature with FBG sensors, if the temperature increases too fast, it will lead to great error, which is mainly caused by the hysteresis of the FBG.

(2) The temperature distribution of the large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composite laminate presents a gradient distribution during the curing process. The temperature of the points located on the outside of the specimen rises first during the heating-up process, decreases first during the cooling-down process. However, the peak temperature value at the point A which located on the outside of the specimen is relatively low (134.18 °C), while the point C which located on the inside of the specimen indicates comparatively higher peak temperature (251.2 °C). Furthermore, point C exhibits the highest temperature and the temperature difference between outer layer and inner layer is 117 °C.

(3) The strain distribution of the large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composite laminate demonstrates a gradient distribution during the curing process. The measured point located on the outside of the specimen shows relatively small residual strain (537.66 $\mu\epsilon$), and it is obvious that the measured points on the boundary are limited by the boundary conditions, additionally, the measured points on the inner side of the composite demonstrate comparatively large residual strain (1180.63 $\mu\epsilon$). The heat of the drastic exothermal reaction was the most significant factor affecting strain of large thickness Kevlar/epoxy composites. Moreover, the maximum difference of curing residual strain between the outer layer and the internal layer is 642.97 $\mu\epsilon$.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Key R & D Program of China (2017YFB0703300).

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Miao, J. Li, Z. Gong, J. Xu, K. He, J. Peng and Y. Cui, Study on the effect of cure cycle on the process induced deformation of cap shaped stiffened composite panels, *Applied Composite Materials*, **20**, 2013, pp. 709-718 (doi: [10.1007/s10443-012-9296-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10443-012-9296-1)).
- [2] Y. Nawab, S. Shahid, N. Boyard and F. Jacquemin, Chemical shrinkage characterization techniques for thermoset resins and associated composites, *Journal of Materials Science*, **48**, 2013, pp. 5387-5409 (doi: [10.1007/s10853-013-7333-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-013-7333-6)).
- [3] O.G. Kravchenko, C. Li, A. Strachan, S.G. Kravchenko and R.B. Pipes, Prediction of the chemical and thermal shrinkage in a thermoset polymer, *Composites Part A*, **66**, 2014, pp. 35-43 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.07.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.07.002)).
- [4] R. Joven, B. Tavakol, A. Rodriguez, M. Guzman and B. Minaie, Characterization of shear stress at the tool-part interface during autoclave processing of prepreg composites, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **129**, 2013, pp. 2017-2028 (doi: [10.1002/app.38909](https://doi.org/10.1002/app.38909)).
- [5] J. Sun, Y. Gu, Y. Li, M. Li and Z. Zhang, Role of tool-part interaction in consolidation of L-shaped laminates during autoclave process, *Applied Composite Materials*, **19**, 2012, pp. 583-597 (doi: [10.1007/s10443-011-9232-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10443-011-9232-9)).
- [6] S. Minakuchi, S. Niwa, K. Takagaki and N. Takeda, Composite cure simulation scheme fully integrating internal strain measurement, *Composites Part A*, **84**, 2016, pp. 53-63 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.01.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.01.001)).
- [7] Y. Qi, D. Jiang, S. Ju and J. Zhang, Investigation of strain history in fast and conventional curing epoxy matrix composites by FBGs, *Composites Science & Technology*, **159**, 2018, pp. 18-24 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.02.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2018.02.019)).
- [8] Q. Wang, L. Gao, X. Wang, Q. Dong and G. Wan, Numerical analysis and fiber Bragg grating monitoring of thermocuring processes of carbon fiber/epoxy laminates, *Polymer Testing*, **62**, 2017, pp. 287-294 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymertesting.2017.07.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2017.07.014)).
- [9] K.S.C. Kuang, R. Kenny, M.P. Whelan, W.J. Cantwell and P.R. Chalker, Residual strain measurement and impact response of optical fibre Bragg grating sensors in fibre metal laminates, *Smart Materials & Structures*, **10**, 2001, pp. 338-346. (doi: [10.1088/0964-1726/10/2/321](https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/10/2/321)).

- [10] L . Rodriguez-Cobo, A Cobo, and J.M. Lopez-Higuera, Embedded compaction pressure sensor based on Fiber Bragg Gratings, *Measurement*, **68**, 2015, pp. 257-261 (doi: [10.1016/j.measurement.2015.02.059](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2015.02.059)).